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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FINANCIAL HEALTH OF ICICI BANK AND AXIS BANK

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ABSTRACT

Banking industry plays an important role in development of a country. Bank is the backbone of a country. International studies showed that Indian banking performing well during recession period of 2008. Purpose of present study is measure and compares the financial performance and health of ICICI bank and Axis bank. Present study is descriptive in nature and researcher take a sample of two banks namely ICICI bank and Axis bank. Present study tries to compare the financial performance of two bank on different parameters like operating profit ratio, earning per share, assets turnover ratio, debt-equity ratio etc. this study purely based on secondary data that gathered from audit annual reports of bank, published research article, newspapers and websites. Study is relevant for the period of 2009-14. Ratio and percentage methods are used for analysis of data. For testing of hypothesis independent sample t-test is used. In the last, researcher concluded that performance of banking industry not only influenced by domestic factors but also a number of international factors influenced the banks performance. Despite all these challenges, we concluded that both performing well on net profit parameter. It also concluded that Axis bank generating more return on net worth compares to its rival ICICI bank. Axis bank performs well on earning per share, assets turnover and debt-equity parameters. Overall performance of Axis bank is good compare to ICICI Banks.

KEYWORDS: Financial performance, Ratio analysis, Independent sample t-test

INTRODUCTION

Banking industry play an important role in developed any country. Bank is the backbone of any country. Every country has need of money for growth. Without money any country cannot developed itself. Growth of a country basically depends on the growth of banks.

Because banks provide the money of industry, agriculture, for making the infrastructure etc. with the help every industry grows. But banks growth depends on its branch increase in country. Banking sector growth measure on increase branch, ATM, deposit, loan, investment, credits limits. In our country, there are 27 public sector banks and 93 commercial banks in India. Any banks financial performance is measured by deposit ratio, solvency ratio, assets, investment and profit etc. If we want to check the performance of any bank for this purpose we compare the performance one bank to another. This study is related to comparison between ICICI bank and Axis bank's financial performance. Both banks are private bank and doing to work in our country. Banking accessibility is provided by private sector banks in also remote area of country. But in this study, researcher want to know which bank is doing better.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is essential tool in research methodology. With the help we find out many variables which can be related for our study. On the basis we get information about last research study which is doing in this sector with help we find out meaning information about our study.

A Vijaya Kumar (2012) this study is related to "Evaluating performance of banks through the CAMEL Model- A case study of State bank of India and its Associates". In this study CAMEL rating Approach has been used for evaluating overall health and financial status SBI and its associate's banks. This study is based on secondary data and data are taken annual report and other resources. Secondary data are taken 1996-97 to 2009-2010. At last this study reveal liquidity position of State bank of India and its associate's bank are better. But State bank of India is edge over associate bank, if compared with each other according to these ratios.

M.Dhanabhakyaam and M. Kavitha (2012) this study is related to "Financial performance of selected public sector banks in India". With the help of this study researcher informed about the public sector banks in India. Six public sector banks are taken in this study. For check the financial performance of banks, ratio analysis, correlation and regression is used. The objective of this study is analysis the financial performance of public sector banks and improving the performance of banks. For completing this objective secondary data are taken

from banking annual report 2001 to 2010 up to. With the help of this study banks performance not only increase but also earn more profit.

Dr.Sonia narula and Monika single (2014) this study is related to “Empirical study on non-performing assets in bank”. To objective are to compare total advance, Net profit Gross NPA , Net NPA and to know the performance of bank and know the relation of net profit and NPA. For this purpose data are collated from the annual report of Punjab national bank of the year 2006-07 to 2011-2012. Systematic research methodology is used. Correlation method are used for the checking the relation of Net profit and NPA. This study is showing NPA and Net profit are continuously increasing and positive relation between NPA and net profit of the some adverse reason. So that bank is not capable to give the loan of its new customer.

D. Padma and V Arulmathi (2013), this study related to “Financial performance of State bank of India and ICICI Bank of India: A Comparative study”. The main objective of study is analysis the financial performance of both banks. For this purpose descriptive research methodology are used. Data are collected of five year up 2006-07 to 2010-2011. This data are taken from the annual report of State Bank of India and ICICI Bank of India. For comparing the both banks performance is taken hypothesis as deposits, Advance, Investment, Net Profit and Total Assets. T test is used as well as tool. With help of t test conclusion is arrived there is significant difference between the financial performance of State Bank of India and ICICI Bank of India. SBI bank is better than ICICI Bank and it is very extensive Bank comparatively.

Sneha and S.Shukla (2015), this study related to “Analysis financial strength of Public and Private sector Banks: A CAMEL Approach”. This study is related to evaluate the performance & financial soundness of various Public & Private sector banks using CAMEL Approach. For this purpose six banks are taken in which three banks are private and three banks are public. Analytical research methodology is used and secondary data are taken up 2010-2013. This data are taken from annual report of public sector (bank of Baroda, IDBI Bank, PNB Bank) and private sector banks (Axis Bank, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank). These studies show the Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management Quality and Earning Quality. With the help of CAMEL Approach every bank has assign the rank in ascending

order. At last conclusion is private sector bank is better public sector bank. In other words financial performance of private sector banks is better comparatively public sector banks.

Srinivas K T (2013), this study is related to “A study of non-performing assets of commercial bank in India”. With the help of this study, researcher informed about the non-performing assets. How it effect the functioning of the banking sector? Main objective of this study identify the non-performing assets and find out the reason for increasing non-performing assets in banking sectors. For study purpose, researcher collected secondary data for the financial year 1996-97 to 2011-2012. In research methodology tabulation method is used and data are collected from RBI bulletin. Core banking solution and proper supervision of borrower are used then NPAs assets are controlled.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To compare and evaluate the financial health of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank.

Hypothesis of study

- $H_{0.1}$:-There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of deposits
- $H_{a.1}$:-There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of deposits
- H_{02} :-There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of loans (Advance).
- $H_{a.2}$:-There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of loans (Advance).
- $H_{0.3}$:-There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of investment.
- $H_{a.3}$:-There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of investment.
- $H_{0.4}$:-There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Profitability.
- $H_{a.4}$:-There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Profitability.
- $H_{0.5}$:-There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of total Assets.

- $H_{a,5}$:-There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of total Assets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design is used in this study.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design of the study is descriptive in nature. It describes data and characteristics associated with Banks. Deliberate sampling design is choose for this study.

AREA OF STUDY

This study is conducted to find out important factors which play important role in checking the performance of banks.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Secondary

For solving the object, Secondary data is collected from audited financial reports of banks, published article, RBI financial bulletin and website. Data is relevant for the financial year from the 2009-10 to 2013-14. Required secondary data is collected from various books, magazines, journals.

SAMPLING METHOD

For study purpose, Judgmental sampling method is taken for data collection. Judgmental sampling method is used by researchers for the purpose of convenience to access information. Judgmental sampling technique is used

SAMPLE SIZE

There are many private banks in whole world. But limitation of the time on the behalf sample of two banks out of 23 private sector bank i.e. ICICI Bank and Axis Bank is drawn.

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

Tabulation methods are used for clearly understood. For the testing of this hypothesis, t-test is used.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table 1: Net Profit Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank (Rs. in crore)

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Net Profit	Net Sale	Net Profit Ratio	Net Profit	Net Sale	Net Profit Ratio
2009-2010	4024.98	33184.58	12.12	2514.53	15603.27	16.11
2010-2011	5153.37	32621.94	15.79	3388.49	19786.94	17.12
2011-2012	6465.25	41045.41	15.75	4242.21	27414.86	15.47
2012-2013	8325.47	48421.31	17.19	5179.43	33733.68	15.35
2013-2014	9810.47	54606.02	17.96	6217.67	38046.38	16.34
	Average		15.76	Average		16.08

Table 1 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The profit of ICICI Bank is increasing continuously but profit of Axis Bank is fluctuating. But comparatively net profit is better of Axis Bank because its average profit is excess instead of ICICI Bank.

Table 2: Operating Profit Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Operating Profit	Net Sale	Operating Profit Ratio	Operating Profit	Net Sale	Operating Profit Ratio
2009-2010	9732	33184.58	29.33	5240.55	15603.27	33.59
2010-2011	9048	32621.94	27.74	6415.69	19786.94	32.42
2011-2012	10386	41045.41	25.30	7430.87	27414.86	27.11
2012-2013	13199	48421.31	27.26	9303.13	33733.68	27.58
2013-2014	16594	54606.02	30.39	11456.09	38046.38	30.11
	Average		28.00	Average		30.16

Table 2 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The Operating profit of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank are fluctuating. But comparatively Operating profit is better of Axis Bank because its average Operating profit is excess instead of ICICI Bank.

Table 3: Return on Net Worth Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Net Profit	Shareholder Fund	Return on Net Worth Ratio	Net Profit	Shareholder Fund	Return on Net Worth Ratio
2009-2010	4024.98	51618.37	7.79	2514.53	16044.62	15.67
2010-2011	5153.37	55090.93	9.35	3388.49	18998.82	17.83
2011-2012	6465.25	60405.24	10.70	4242.21	22808.54	18.59
2012-2013	8325.47	66705.95	12.48	5179.43	33107.86	15.64
2013-2014	9810.47	73213.33	13.40	6217.67	38220.49	16.26
	Average		10.75	Average		16.80

Table 3 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The Return on Net Worth Ratio of ICICI Bank is continuously increasing but Axis Bank's Net Worth ratio is fluctuating. But comparatively Net return is better of Axis Bank because its average Return on Net worth Ratio is excess instead of ICICI Bank.

Table 4: Earning per Share of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Net profit	No. of equity	Earnings per Share	Net profit	No. of equity	Earnings per Share
2009-2010	4024.98	111.48	36.10	2514.53	40.51	62.07
2010-2011	5153.37	115.17	44.75	3388.49	41.05	82.55
2011-2012	6465.25	115.27	56.09	4242.21	41.32	102.67
2012-2013	8325.47	115.35	72.18	5179.43	46.79	110.70
2013-2014	9810.47	115.48	84.95	6217.67	46.98	132.35
	Average		58.81	Average		98.07

Table 4 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The earnings per share of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank are continuously increasing. But comparatively earnings per share are better of Axis Bank because its average earnings per share are excess instead of ICICI Bank.

Table 5: Total Assets Turnover Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Net Sale	Total Assets	Total Assets Turnover Ratio	Net Sale	Total Assets	Total Assets Turnover Ratio
2009-2010	33184.58	363399.72	9.13	15603.27	180647.9	8.64
2010-2011	32621.94	406233.69	8.03	19786.94	242713.4	8.15
2011-2012	41045.41	489068.81	8.39	27414.86	285627.8	9.60
2012-2013	48421.31	536794.68	9.02	33733.68	340560.7	9.91
2013-2014	54606.02	594641.58	9.18	38046.38	383244.9	9.93
	Average		8.75	Average		9.24

Table 5 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The total Assets Turnover Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank are fluctuating. But comparatively total Assets

Turnover Ratio is better of Axis Bank because its average total Assets Turnover Ratio excess instead of ICICI Bank.

Table 6: Dividend Pay-out Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Dividend Per Equity share	Earnings per share	Dividend Pay-out Ratio	Dividend Per Equity share	Earnings per share	Dividend Pay-out Ratio
2009-2010	12.0	36.10	33.23	12.0	65.78	18.24
2010-2011	14.0	44.74	31.28	14.0	82.95	16.87
2011-2012	16.5	56.08	29.41	16.0	102.94	15.54
2012-2013	20.0	72.17	27.71	18.0	119.67	15.04
2013-2014	23.0	84.95	27.07	20.0	132.56	15.08
	Average		29.75	Average		16.16

Table 6 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The dividend payout Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank are continuously decreasing. But comparatively Dividend pay-out Ratio is better of ICICI Bank because its average Dividend Pay-out Ratio excess instead of Axis Bank.

Table 7: Debt-Equity Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Outsider's Fund	Shareholder Fund	Debt Equity Ratio	Outsider's Fund	Shareholder Fund	Debt Equity Ratio
2009-2010	202016.61	51618.37	3.91	141300.22	16044.62	8.81
2010-2011	225602.11	55090.93	4.10	189237.87	18998.82	9.96
2011-2012	255499.95	60405.24	4.23	220104.31	22808.54	9.65
2012-2013	292613.63	66705.95	4.39	252613.59	33107.86	7.63
2013-2014	331913.66	73213.33	4.53	280944.56	38220.49	7.35
	Average		4.23	Average		8.68

Table 7 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The debt equity Ratio of ICICI Bank is continuously increasing and Axis Bank is fluctuating. This ratio shows solvency capacity of the any organization. But comparatively Debt equity Ratio is better of ICICI Bank because it's average Debt equity Ratio less instead of Axis Bank. It means that axis bank are maximum time depend its Debt which is not better for any organization. On this condition organization cannot pay loan proper time.

Table 8: Proprietary Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Shareholder Fund	Total Assets	Proprietary Ratio	Shareholder Fund	Total Assets	Proprietary Ratio
2009-2010	51618.37	363399.7	0.14	16044.62	180647.8	0.09
2010-2011	55090.93	406233.6	0.14	18998.82	242713.3	0.08
2011-2012	60405.24	489068.8	0.12	22808.54	285627.7	0.08
2012-2013	66705.95	536794.6	0.12	33107.86	340560.6	0.10
2013-2014	73213.33	594641.5	0.12	38220.49	383244.8	0.10
	Average		0.13	Average		0.09

Table 8 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The Proprietary Ratio of ICICI Bank is continuously decreasing but Proprietary Ratio of Axis Bank is fluctuating. But comparatively Proprietary Ratio is better of ICICI Bank because it's average Proprietary Ratio excess instead of Axis Bank.

Table 9: Interest expended to Interest earned Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	Interest Expanded	Interest Earned	Ratio	Interest Expanded	Interest Earned	Ratio
2009-2010	17592.57	25706.93	0.68	6633.53	11638.02	0.57
2010-2011	16957.15	25974.05	0.65	8591.82	15154.81	0.57
2011-2012	22808.49	33542.65	0.68	13976.91	21994.65	0.64
2012-2013	26209.18	40075.59	0.65	17516.31	27182.57	0.64
2013-2014	27702.58	44178.15	0.63	18689.52	30641.15	0.61
	Average		0.66	Average		0.61

Table 9 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The Interest expended to Interest Earned Ratio of ICICI Bank is fluctuating but Interest expended to Interest earned Ratio of Axis Bank is continuously increasing. But comparatively Interest expended to Interest earned Ratio is better of ICICI Bank because it's average Interest expended to Interest earned instead of Axis Bank.

Table 10: Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Year	ICICI BANK			AXIS BANK		
	NPA	Advance	Ratio	NPA	Advance	Ratio
2009-2010	3901	181206	2.153	419.00	104343.12	0.402
2010-2011	2458	216366	1.136	410.35	142407.83	0.288
2011-2012	1894	253728	0.746	472.64	169754.54	0.278
2012-2013	2234	290249	0.776	704.13	196965.96	0.357
2013-2014	3301	338702	0.975	1024.60	230066.76	0.445
	Average		1.157	Average		0.354

Table 10 shows the financial performance of ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank. The Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of ICICI Bank is fluctuating but Net NPA to Net Advance ratio is better of Axis bank. But average NPA to net advance ratio of ICICI bank is greater than axis bank. So the performance of Axis bank is better.

Table 11: Financial performance evaluation of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank through t-test

Variables	Mean 1	Mean 2	d.f.	C.V.	Critical value ($\alpha= 5\%$)
Deposit	261529.2	216840.094	8	1.328	2.306
Advance	256050.2	168708.208	8	2.491	2.306
Investment	152671.0	89688.900	8	4.007	2.306
Net Profit	6755.5	4308.466	8	1.985	2.306
Total Assets	478027.7	286558.912	8	3.471	2.306

		t-test for equality of means		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
deposit	Equal variances assumed	1.328	8	.221
	Equal variances not assumed	1.328	7.982E0	.221
advance	Equal variances assumed	2.491	8	.037
	Equal variances not assumed	2.491	7.580E0	.039
investment	Equal variances assumed	4.007	8	.004
	Equal variances not assumed	4.007	7.975E0	.004
Net profit	Equal variances assumed	1.985	8	.082
	Equal variances not assumed	1.985	6.691E0	.089
Total assets	Equal variances assumed	3.471	8	.008
	Equal variances not assumed	3.471	7.787E0	.009

Testing of Hypothesis for deposit of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Calculating value of t-statistics is 1.328 and critical value of t-statistics is 2.306 at 5% level of significance. Calculated value of t-statistics lies in the acceptance region and it indicates that at 5% level of significance null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of deposits” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to accept the null hypothesis and reject alternate. It also inferred from the above that there have no statistical differences between financial performance of ICICI bank and Axis bank in term of deposit.

Testing of Hypothesis for Advance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Calculating value of t-statistics is 2.491 and critical value of t-statistics is 2.306 at 5% level of significance. Calculated value of t-statistics does not lie in the acceptance region and it indicates that at 5% level of significance alternate hypothesis “There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Advance” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to accept the alternate hypothesis and reject null. It also inferred from the above that there have enough statistical differences between financial performance of ICICI bank and Axis bank in term of Advance. It also indicates that ICICI bank performing better than its rival bank.

Testing of Hypothesis for Investment of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Calculating value of t-statistics is 4.007 and critical value of t-statistics is 2.306 at 5% level of significance. Calculated value of t-statistics does not lie in the acceptance region and it indicates that at 5% level of significance alternate hypothesis “There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Investment” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to accept the alternate hypothesis and reject null. It also inferred from the above that there have enough statistical differences between financial performance of ICICI bank and Axis bank in term of Investment. It also indicates that ICICI bank performing better than its rival bank.

Testing of Hypothesis for Net Profit of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Calculating value of t-statistics is 1.985 and critical value of t-statistics is 2.306 at 5% level of significance. Calculated value of t-statistics lies in the acceptance region and it indicates that at 5% level of significance null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Net Profit” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to accept the null hypothesis and reject alternate. It also inferred from the above that there have no statistical differences between financial performance of ICICI bank and Axis bank in term of Net Profit.

Testing of Hypothesis for Total Assets of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank

Calculating value of t-statistics is 3.471 and critical value of t-statistics is 2.306 at 5% level of significance. Calculated value of t-statistics does not lie in the acceptance region and it indicates that at 5% level of significance alternate hypothesis “There is significant difference between the performance of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank in term of Total Assets” is accepted and there have enough statistical evidence to accept the alternate hypothesis and reject null. It also inferred from the above that there have enough statistical differences between financial performance of ICICI bank and Axis bank in term of Total Assets. It also indicates that ICICI bank performing better than its rival bank.

FINDINGS

This study provide the some key factor on the behalf we take some important decision.

- The average Net Profit of ICICI Bank is 15.76 and Axis Bank is 16.08, which is the more than 0.32 of ICICI bank. It means that axis bank's performance is better than of ICICI bank.
- The average Operating Profit of ICICI Bank is 28.00 and Axis Bank is 30.16, which is more than 2.16 of ICICI bank. It means that Axis Bank's performance is better than of ICICI bank.
- The average Return on Net worth of ICICI bank is 10.75 and Axis bank is 16.80, which is more than 6.05 of ICICI bank. It means that Axis bank performance is better than of ICICI bank. In other word, Axis bank's shareholder earn 6.05 % more money comparatively ICICI bank.
- The average Earning Per Share of ICICI bank is 58.81 and Axis bank is 98.07, which is more than 39.26 of ICICI bank. It means that Earning Per Share of Axis bank is better than ICICI bank.
- The average Total Assets Turnover ratio of ICICI bank 8.75% and Axis Bank is 9.24%, which is more than 0.49% of ICICI bank.
- The average Dividend Pay Share of ICICI bank is Rs.29.75 and Axis bank is Rs.16.16. In this condition, dividend payout ratio of ICICI bank is Rs.13.59 more than Axis bank. In other word, we can say that ICICI bank are paying more dividend comparatively Axis bank.
- The average Debt Equity ratio of ICICI bank is 4.23 and Axis bank is 8.68, which is the 4.45% excess of ICICI bank. In other word Axis bank pays its debt 4.45% more ICICI bank.
- The average Proprietary Ratio of ICICI bank is 0.13 and Axis bank is 0.09, which is more than 0.04 of Axis bank. It means that ICICI bank performance is better.
- The average Interest Expended to Interest Earned ratio of ICICI bank is 0.66 and Axis bank is 0.61. It is 0.05% excess of ICICI bank ratio than the Axis bank.
- The average Net NPA to Net advance ratio of ICICI bank is 1.157 and Axis bank is 0.354. It is 0.803% excess of ICICI bank ratio than the Axis bank.

CONCLUSION

International studies showed that Indian Banking industry performing well amidst global economic growth slowdown. It is very difficult to measure the performance of banks on few parameters. Today, banks facing rapid changing environment. Performance of banking

industry not only influenced by domestic factors but also a number of international factors influenced the banks performance. Despite all these challenges, we concluded that both performing well on net profit parameter. It also concluded that Axis bank generating more return on net worth compares to its rival ICICI bank. Axis bank performs well on earning per share, assets turnover and debt-equity parameters. Overall performance of Axis bank is good compare to ICICI Banks.

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